

Echoes of Destruction:

Urbicide in the heart of Prishtina

Master thesis

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I sincerely hope never to disappoint you.

Abstract

This case study aims to trace urbicide in Kosovo, specifically in the historical core of Prishtina during and after Yugoslavia. During this span, Prishtina goes through an era of transition not only in governance but also in architecture. The creation of a socialist, modern city based on Yugoslav principles also meant the demolition of the past through the destruction of Albanian architectural heritage and, during the war, the destruction of roots. Through a multidisciplinary approach, this research aims to illuminate the complications of urbicide in the heart of Prishtina and its implications for the present and future of the city.

But was urbicide achieved? How did Prishtina go through different stages of urban planning to form what it is today, and why was the historical zone used for modernisation? Strategies were used not only as a tool of fear but also to establish Serbian control over the territory, by not adhering to urban plans and creating a half-baked Prishtina. The study begins by providing an overview of the phenomenon of urbicide, followed by an analysis of historical interpretations of urbicide in Kosovo caused by the Albanian-Serbian conflict. Then, the identification of parallels and overlaps with other countries of the former Yugoslavia that also suffered the same fate. All this centers on the capital—the tracking of urbicide through quantitative analysis along waves of urban development and how this affected Prishtina's identity.

As a result, it aspired to prove urbicide in Prishtina during the Yugoslav period—through what is left behind, collective memory, documents or photographs—to achieve the complete picture of what happened to Prishtina, the genesis of its identity, and how conflicts and politics affected the Prishtina dream. As a final result, an alternative reality will be created—if urbicide did not happen, what kind of Prishtina would we have?

Key words: *urbicide, Prishtina, old town Prishtina, war, architecture, loss of identity, erosion of memory, urban destruction.*

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Introduction

Located in the heart of the Balkans, Prishtina is a vibrant and culturally rich urban center. The urban evolution of the capital of Kosovo is a story intertwined with a turbulent history, cultural heritage and socio-political dynamics. As a city that has experienced centuries of transitions, Prishtina's urban identity has evolved through the ages, each leaving its mark on the city's urban landscape. However, between the layers of historical narratives and architectural heritage lies the tale of defeat, the loss of identity.

Prishtina's genesis dates back to antiquity as a modest settlement in the Dardanian Kingdom. A strategic crossroads connecting the Adriatic Sea with the Danube River, it has undergone successive waves of change, shaped by occupiers ranging from the Roman, Byzantine, Ottoman and Yugoslav periods. Contributing to the creation of a mosaic of architectural styles, religious monuments and urban spaces. However, despite this rich heritage, Prishtina's urban identity has been profoundly influenced by external forces, especially during periods of conflict and political upheaval.

The 20th century stands as a defining chapter in Prishtina's history, the end of World War II found Kosovo as a *"motherless state"* and the Federal People's Republic of Yugoslavia under Josip Broz Tito took advantage of this situation by incorporating it as a province. Over the course of 45 years, Kosovo experienced changes in governance, architecture and identity. Prishtina as the capital took rapid steps towards becoming a socialist city with the slogan *"Destroy the old, build the new"*, the city underwent development and modernisation based on socialist principle but destroying the city's own indigenous past. However, this period laid the foundation for tensions that grew in intensity day by day until the outbreak of the violent conflict of the 1990s. A war that resulted in irreversible damage to the city's physical fabric and collective memory. As bombs destroyed buildings and bullets ricocheted through the streets, the very essence of Prishtina's identity was shattered, leaving behind scars of loss and displacement.

The consequences of urbicide in Prishtina extend beyond physical destruction. As such, it includes profound socio-economic, cultural, and psychological impacts on its inhabitants.

Displacement of communities, loss of heritage and fragmentation of urban life have presented complex challenges for reconstruction. This thesis aims to critically analyze the phenomenon of urbicide in the center of Prishtina, examining its historical roots, the tactics used during the war and the lasting legacies in post-conflict reconstruction. By delving into the narratives of Prishtina's development up to its "*destruction*", it seeks to shed light on its dimensions and the implications arising from the conflict. This introduces us to the term "*urbicide*", the war that Kosovo experienced not only with loss of people but also with architecture.

Purpose and objectives

The purpose of this thesis is to critically analyze and examine the evolution of urbanization in Prishtina, what was planned and what was ruined by the idea of creating a living city. With a special focus on the meaning of the loss of identity through urbicide caused by the occupiers. By delving into the past, present and future trajectories of the city, this study aims to shed light on the complex interplay of socio-political, cultural and economic factors that have shaped the urban landscape of Prishtina. It aims to provide insights into the challenges and opportunities for preserving and recovering the city's unique identity amidst rapid urbanization, globalization and post-conflict reconstruction efforts.

Objectives:

1. Analyzing the historical evolution of Old Prishtina's urban fabric, from its origins to its transformation during and after the Yugoslav period.
2. To examine the cultural, social, and political dimensions of Old Prishtina's urban identity and how they were affected by urbicide.
3. To assess the impact of external forces such as conflict, modernization, and urban restructuring on the destruction and alteration of Old Prishtina.
4. To identify strategies and opportunities for preserving and revitalizing the cultural heritage and collective memory of Old Prishtina in the face of past and ongoing urbicide.

Research questions

- 1. Was the old town of Prishtina a victim of this phenomenon and if so, what resulted from it in preserving the identity and history of the city?*
- 2. What were the specific targets of urbicide and why were certain urban areas and monuments in Prishtina selected for demolition?*
- 3. How does urbicide in the heart of Prishtina compare to similar cases of urban destruction in other cities within Yugoslavia during this period?*
- 4. What shape does old Prishtina have today after urbicide, in terms of urban landscape and collective identity?*

Methods and steps of the work

Step 1: Review of regional and global literature and documentation regarding the phenomenon of urbicide, its causes, impacts and consequences for city building in countries emerging from conflict. In this phase, an interpretative historical study will be conducted examining the complexity and implications of this destructive phenomenon within the context of conflict and war. From the very notion, when it is accepted as a principle that it has happened and is happening, to the consequences it leaves.

Step 2: Interpretive and historical analysis by tracing the urbicide caused by the Albanian-Serbian conflict during the Yugoslav period and the results of the same in Kosovo, respectively in Pristina. Also through a comparative analysis of this phenomenon with other countries of the former Yugoslavia such as: Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, etc. In order to identify parallels and overlaps from this event in creating defeat in architecture.

Step 3: Continuing with quantitative and qualitative analysis with a narrower focus on Pristina, the three waves of urban development and tracing the genocide in architecture along them, affecting the damage to the identity of what Pristina residents actually know and remember as Pristina. This will be achieved through interviews with citizens. During this phase, these spaces will also be researched and coordinated, whether they exist physically or only spiritually in memory.

Step 4: In conclusion, the aim is to conclude the “*aftermath*” of urbicide in Pristina through comparative analyses of the past with the present and what is intended as an alternative for the future of Pristina. Documentation through photographs, archival documents of what Pristina lost from urbicide and what if the same had not happened. How different would Pristina be from today?

Expected results

This thesis aims to prove whether there was urbicide in old town Pristina, during the period under Yugoslav rule. Through tracing what is left behind, be it collective memory, documents or photographs, the completion of the full picture of what happened to Pristina, the genesis of its identity and how political conflicts contributed to the extinction of the Pristina dream of a visionary and metropolitan Pristina as planned in the 1970s. As a final result, an alternative reality will be created if urbicide had not occurred, what kind of Pristina would we have?

The phenomenon
of **urbicide**

01.

“Destroy
the old,
build the
new”

**Urbicide in Kosovo
during Yugoslavia**

Beyond the ruins.

Urbicide
in the heart of
Prishtina

03.

Conclusions and recommendations

This study set out to explore the phenomenon of urbicide, specifically questioning whether Prishtina was a victim of such deliberate destruction. By analyzing changes in the urban landscape during the Yugoslav period and the Kosovo War, it examined the attacks on physical structures and their implications for the city's cultural identity and collective memory. The thesis argues that the targeted destruction of architecture was not merely a consequence of war or a byproduct of modernization, but a deliberate assault on the cultural and historical identity of Kosovo's Albanian population, a strategic attempt to erase the past and destabilize the symbolic foundations of the city.

The primary findings reveal that the uprooting of cultural monuments, religious structures, and historic neighborhoods, such as the destruction of the Prishtina Bazaar (Çarshia), the Small Hammam, the Llokaç Mosque, and the Church of Saint Anthony—were calculated efforts to sever the community's connection to its heritage. This aligns with Robert Bevan's concept of cultural cleansing as a weapon of war. The loss of such symbolic spaces has left enduring gaps in the city's collective memory and complicated the process of post-war recovery. In this way, the destruction undermined the city's very essence, reflecting a broader agenda of cultural erasure in which the remnants of the past are not only physically removed but rendered invisible in public consciousness.

The impact of urbicide in Prishtina underscores the critical role of architecture not merely as physical infrastructure but as a vessel of cultural continuity and identity—a repository of heritage whose loss produces not only material destruction but also profound psychological and social consequences. This research highlights the depth of urbicide's impact on Prishtina, yet it also acknowledges its limitations. Due to the scope of the study and the scarcity of focused material on urbicide in Prishtina, not all affected sites beyond the capital were explored, nor was the full range of community responses analyzed. Furthermore, while this thesis concentrated primarily on architectural loss, future research might examine other dimensions of cultural erasure, such as the loss of intangible heritage and traditions once rooted in these physical spaces. Future studies should also consider the role of contemporary urban planning

in addressing these voids and the challenge of balancing modernization with heritage preservation in a post-conflict context.

The implications of this thesis emphasize the urgent need to protect and honor architectural heritage as a means of preserving collective memory and fostering resilience. The case of Prishtina serves as a powerful example of the destructive effects of urbicide, illustrating how the obliteration of the urban landscape can function as a form of erasing a city itself. As Prishtina continues its path of urban renewal, a balanced approach, one that respects historical continuity while addressing modern needs, is essential. Such a path may help restore a sense of identity and belonging, allowing the community to heal and rebuild in a way that acknowledges the past and promotes an inclusive future.

Ultimately, this thesis has contributed to a deeper understanding of urbicide as a deliberate strategy for cultural annihilation, one that seeks to erase history and the identity of a people, and how this strategy unfolded in Prishtina. The lessons from Prishtina illustrate the vital role of architecture in maintaining social and cultural continuity and the profound impact that loss has on a community's heritage and memory. The destructive potential of urbicide serves as a stark reminder of the challenges of reconstruction and cultural representation. The insights gained through this research demonstrate that Prishtina was indeed targeted by urbicide, particularly during the early decades of Yugoslav rule up until its end, destruction that did not end with the physical dismantling of buildings but left lasting imprints on social and psychological discourse.

Today, as the city continues to evolve, a thoughtful and balanced urban strategy, one that honors the past and promotes a flexible urban identity, is essential for cultivating a sustainable future and healing the wounds of the past. What we learn from the urbicide in Prishtina is not solely darkness and devastation; rather, it reminds us of the importance of architecture in embodying and preserving the soul of a community of maintaining the identity of Prishtina.

Literature

1. Abdullahu, D. (2024) In the footsteps of Prishtina's origins, Prishtina in History (I). Available at: <https://www.prishtinanehistori.org/article/224/ne-gjurme-te-origjines-se-prishtines> (Accessed: 25 June 24)
2. Al- Shoubaki, Hind.(2022) War Victims and the Right to a City; From Damascus to Zaatari. Springer Nature.
3. Araz, S.D. (2024) "urbicide": Erasing Palestinian memory beyond Gaza's ruins, TRT World - Breaking News, Live Coverage, Opinions and Videos. Available at: <https://www.trtworld.com/magazine/urbicide-erasing-palestinian-memory-beyond-gazas-ruins-17809785> (Accessed: 9 April 2024).
4. Armstrong, K. (2011) Jerusalem: One city, three faiths. Random House Publishing Group.
5. Bajgora, S. (2014). "The Destruction of Islamic Heritage in the Kosovo War, 1998-1999". Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Kosovo, Pristina.
6. The Islamic Community of Kosovo (2000) "Serbian Barbarity against Islamic Monuments in Kosovo". Islamic Knowledge. Pristina.
7. Berman, M., (1982). *All That Is Solid Melts Into Air: The Experience of Modernity*. New York: Simon and Schuster.
8. Bevan, R. (2006). *The Destruction of Memory Architecture at War*. London, UK: Reaktion Books.
9. Bytyqi, V. (2023) The 24th anniversary of the NATO bombings is remembered with mixed emotions and feelings, Koha.net. Available at: <https://www.koha.net/en/arberi/kujtohet-me-emocione-e-ndjenja-te-perziera-24-vjetori-i-bombardimeve-te-nato-s> (Accessed: 11 September 2024).
10. Carrión, F. (2018) "Urbicide, or the city's liturgical death", Oculum Ensaïos.
11. Chapple, A. (2023) Over troubled water: The fall and rise of Mostar's bridge, RadioFreeEurope/RadioLiberty. Available at: <https://www.rferl.org/a/mostar-bridge-30-years-destroyed-restored/32677921.html> (Accessed: 04 April 2024).
12. Clark, H. (2000) Civil resistance in Kosovo. London: Pluto Press.
13. Compagnoni, A.S.M. and Adam (2023) Urbicide and the Russian-Ukrainian war " Wavell room, Wavell Room. Available at:

<https://wavellroom.com/2023/04/05/urbicide-russian-ukrainian-war/>
(Accessed: 15 April 2024).

14. Coward, M. (2010) *Urbicide: The politics of urban destruction*. London: Routledge.
15. Hadžimuhamedović A. (2019) Participative reconstruction as a healing process in Bosnia. Available at https://www.researchgate.net/publication/335586739_Participative_reconstruction_as_a_healing_process_in_Bosnia. Accessed: 5 April 2024.
16. Halitaj, A. (2024) What is known about the damages caused to Kosovo in the war?, Report Corruption! KALLXO.com. Available at: https://kallxo.com/lajm/cfare-dihet-per-demet-qe-iu-shkaktuan-kosoves-ne-lufte/?fbclid=IwAR3LMrav7K5B26BvfiVnCSUI73cDLSajnRHFYhVtfC5smRUbLyXgc_jUFc_aem_AWG7kuntFejq62yDIB63I27GpUhQmTQKSVcMjSZLc8KWjpRZ4b73uJUG3qqyBqUSB9jm62Zqt95S4I2NGZLZ2TYv (Accessed: 15 June 2024).
17. Hayruddin, M. (2017) Old bridge in Mostar, Architectuul. Available at: <https://architectuul.com/architecture/old-bridge-in-mostar> (Accessed: 04 April 2024).
18. Herscher, A. (2020) *Violence taking place: The architecture of the Kosovo conflict*. Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press.
19. Herscher, A., Riedlmayer, A. (2000) - *Monument and crime, the destruction of Historic Architecture in Kosovo*. Grey Room, Inc. and Massachusetts Institute of Technology, pp. 108–122.
20. Hoti, S., Jerliu, F. and Llonçari, X. (2020) "Kosovo Architecture among Social Mutations "Balkanization" of (Re)constructions", *Le monde diplomatique*.
21. Hoxha, E (2008) "The Redemption of the "Urbanization" Past in Prishtina's Legacy. *ChwB*
22. Hoxha, T. (2016) Prishtina Orthodox Church should be turned into a museum, *Prishtina Insight*. Available at: <https://prishtinainsight.com/orthodox>
23. Islami, A.(2024) Prishtina during the Ottoman period (1455-1912). *Prishtina in History*. Available at <https://www.prishtinanehistori.org/article/137/prishtina-gjate-kohes-osmane-1455-1912> (Accessed 25 June 2024)
24. Israel gaza war: History of the conflict explained (2024) BBC News. Available at: <https://www.bbc.com/news/newsbeat-44124396> (Accessed 9 April 2024).

25. Jashari-Kajtazi, T. Jakupi, A. (2017) Interpretation of architectural identity through landmark architecture: The case of Prishtina, Kosovo from the 1970s to the 1980s. *Frontiers of Architectural Research*
26. Jerliu, F., (2024), "The tale of unfinished urbanization" Festival dell'Architettura Magazine.
27. Jerliu, F., Navakazi, V. (2018) The Socialist Modernization of Prishtina-interrogating types of urban and architectural contributions to the city, *Mesto a dejiny Journal*.
28. Kachmar, O. (2023) Russia's campaign of urbicide in Ukraine, *New Lines Institute*. Available at: <https://newlinesinstitute.org/power-vacuums/russias-campaign-of-urbicide-in-ukraine/> (Accessed on: 17 April 2024).
29. Kalia, S. (2023) A brief history of the term "urbicide", *The Hindu*. Available at: <https://www.thehindu.com/news/international/a-brief-history-of-the-term-urbicide/article67576893.ece> (Accessed: 11 March 2024).
30. Municipality of Prishtina (2018) *Narrative of Prishtina, A Concise History of Prishtina*.
31. Kraja, G. (2016) A symbol of repression which should remain just that, *Kosovo 2.0*. Retrieved from: <https://kosovotwopointzero.com/en/a-symbol-of-repression-which-should-remain-just-that/> (Accessed: 06 October 2024).
32. Krasniqi, J. (2010) *Kosovo after the Second World War, Bota Sot*.
33. Llapit Mosque: IRCICA (2020) *IRCICA | ISLAMIC ARCHITECTURAL HERITAGE DATABASE*. Retrieved from: <https://www.islamicarchitecturalheritage.com/listings/llapit-mosque> (Accessed: 29 September 2024).
34. Llonçari, Xh. (2016) "Urbicide and how the church in the UP courtyard became part of this phenomenon", *Telegrafi*.
35. Mezentsev K., Mezentsev O. (2022). *War and the city: Lessons from urbicide in Ukraine*. *Czasopismo Geograficzne*.
36. Oral History Kosova (2018). 8 December "Mahmut Mumci, Interview/Part One". Watch at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0upzZDerHBE>
37. Oral History Kosova (2019). 13 January "Sevim Baki, Interview/Part 1". Available at

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gskMNQi159I-church-museum-kosovos-recent-history/> (Accessed: 06 October 2024).

38. Oral History Kosova (2019). 26 June "Jakup Qeshmexhiu, Interview/Part 1". Available at <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KENkQURjMTA&t=156s>. Accessed 26 September 2024)
39. Ordev, Igor (2008) Erasing the Past: Destruction and Preservation of Cultural Heritage in Former Yugoslavia: Part 1, Occasional Papers on Religion in Eastern Europe: Vol. 28 : Iss. 4, Article 2. Available at: <https://digitalcommons.georgefox.edu/ree/vol28/iss4/2>.
40. Porteous, D. and Smith, S.E. (2014) Domicide: The global destruction of home. Montréal: McGill-Queen's University Press.
41. Riedlmayer, A. (1995) Erasing the past: The destruction of libraries and archives in Bosnia-Herzegovina, Middle East Studies Association Bulletin, 29(1), pp. 7–11, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/23061201>.
42. Riedlmayer, András (2007). "Crimes of War, Crimes of Peace: Destruction of Libraries during and after the Balkan Wars of the 1990s
43. Roos, D. (2024) A volcanic eruption was not the only disaster that destroyed Pompeii, History.com. Available at: <https://www.history.com/news/pompeii-eruption-volcano-earthquakes> (Accessed on: 03 March 2024)
44. Team, J.S. (2022) The destruction of Jerusalem's Moroccan Quarter: From centuries-old Maghrebi community to Western Wall Prayer Plaza, Jerusalem Story Project. Available at: <https://www.jerusalemstory.com/en/article/destruction-jerusalems-moroccan-quarter-centuries-old-maghrebi-community-western-wall> (Accessed: 10 March 2024).
45. Teijgeler, René (2006). "Preserving cultural heritage in times of conflict"

46. What is marxism? definition of marxism, marxism meaning (undated) The Economic Times. Available at: <https://economictimes.indiatimes.com/definition/marxism> (Accessed on: 22 May 2024).
47. Wilkes, John J. (1995). *The Illyrians* Oxford, United Kingdom: Blackwell Publishers Limited.
48. Xami Llokaçit (no date) Oral History Kosovo. Available at: https://oralhistorykosovo.org/sq/points_of_interests/xhamia-e-lokacit-2/ (Accessed: 12 August 2024).
49. Yugoslavia (2024) Encyclopædia Britannica. Available at: <https://www.britannica.com/place/Yugoslavia-former-federated-nation-1929-2003> (Accessed: 22 May 2024).